

Vernacular Language Teaching in Vanuatu: perspectives from three communities

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19 April 2024

Funded by the Economic and Social Research Council's Impact Acceleration Account at the University of Surrey, UK.

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1. Introduction

We undertook a vernacular literacy education survey with teachers from three language communities in Vanuatu. Our main objective was to understand more about the experiences of using the local vernacular language as the Medium of Instruction (MOI). Though this research is a pilot study, the results are intended to inform current education policy. In particular the study's main aims are to understand:

1. Teachers' perspectives on speaking and using the main community language in the classroom and what training they require.
2. How many children speak the main community language in each community and their enjoyment of using the language in the classroom.
3. What further teaching resources are essential for effectively using the community language as the MOI.

2. Acknowledgements

We wish to thank Helen Tamtam from the Curriculum Development Unit and Prof. Robert Early from the University of the South Pacific for their collaboration in developing the survey. We wish to acknowledge the help given from the three language communities of North Ambrym, Lewo and Merei, in particular, for the support from Yanick Tekon, Simeon Ben and Adam Pike. Furthermore, we wish to thank Mabel Baldry and Emily Marsh for the infographics. Finally, thank you to Penny Everson for her help in preparing the document.

3. Background

The Vanuatu National Language Policy supports the use of community languages in education.¹ Vanuatu is the most linguistically dense country in the world, with over 130 indigenous vernacular languages² and therefore efforts to implement vernacular languages in education require immense resources. One of the aims of the Vanuatu Education Support Program³ (VESP) was to implement a move towards a model of using either local vernacular languages or Bislama in the first two years of education in primary schools, followed by a transition to either English or French in year three. One of the main outcomes of VESP in this regard was the production and translation of literacy materials into 46 languages aimed at the first two years of primary education. Languages with over 2000 speakers were identified as being the optimal choice for the rollout of vernacular language materials, representing 86% of the population.

It has now been more than a decade since the introduction of the Vanuatu National Language Policy in 2012. However, there is limited information on what vernacular literacy materials are currently in circulation in the primary school system or how well-equipped teachers are in using the vernacular as the MOI. This survey was designed to understand how to build on the earlier successes of VESP and continue the momentum of implementing a vernacular language policy in such a linguistically diverse country.

We note that VESP is currently working with the CDU to develop a longitudinal study to research the extent to which schools adopt the use of vernacular languages in six communities and how this impacts student engagement and the learning of English and French.⁴ Proposed studies such as this will give more in-depth findings than those we present here. However, we believe that our findings will provide a base for longer term studies such as these.

4. Methodology

4.1 Design

The [Vanuatu Literacy, Language and Teacher Training Survey](#) was designed in English and Bislama to cover the main objectives listed in the introduction. We collaborated with representatives from the University of

¹ Vanuatu National Language Policy. 2012. Ministry of Education.

² François, A., Franjeh, M., Lacrampe, S., & Schnell, S. 2015. The exceptional linguistic density of Vanuatu. In A. François, S. Lacrampe, M. Franjeh, S. Schnell (eds), *The Languages of Vanuatu: Unity and Diversity*. Studies in the Languages of Island Melanesia, 5. Canberra: Asia-Pacific Linguistics. Pp. 1-21.

³ Early R., & Tamtam H. 2015. VESP Language Policy Implementation Plan Second Draft, August 2015. Ministry of Education and Training, Vanuatu.

⁴ VESP: Vanuatu Education Support Program. August 2023. Quarters 1 and 2 Progress Report.

the South Pacific and the Curriculum Development Unit to ensure the questions and findings would be relevant.

We used a mixed methods approach, collecting and analysing both qualitative and quantitative data. The language communities chosen for the study were known by the lead author, Dr Franjeh, who has been conducting linguistic research and creating vernacular literacy materials in these areas for several years, with the support of the Vanuatu Cultural Centre. The three communities surveyed included two communities that had vernacular literacy materials developed during the original VESP project (Vatlongos and Rral, both spoken on Ambrym). We also surveyed the Merei language community (Santo), which was not included in the original VESP project (Merei, spoken on Santo) as a point of comparison.

The lead researcher visited schools in the Vatlongos (South East Ambrym), Rral (North Ambrym), and Merei (Santo) language communities and conducted the survey with principals and teachers of primary schools and kindergartens. Data was collected in July 2023.

4.2 Research questions

We had three main research questions related to our main aims. Each research question has a related sub-question:

1. How confident are the teachers in using the main community language as the MOI?
 - What training is required to improve teachers' confidence?
2. Do children enjoy being taught in the main community language?
 - What aspects of the main community language do children find hard?
3. What vernacular literacy materials are available to teachers?
 - What future resources are required to use the main community language effectively in schools?

4.3 Sample

We aimed to interview the principals and the teachers of class one and two for each primary school in each language community. However, it was not always possible to meet this target (see limitations below) and we interviewed teachers who were present on the day of the survey.

In total we interviewed 33 teachers across 13 schools in the three language communities. Overall, the teachers surveyed taught 614 students. Both the Rral and Vatlongos communities had been included in the MoET's Vanuatu Education Sector Programme (VESP) and had literacy materials developed for them. Furthermore, the Rral community has had a dictionary and over 40 different literacy books developed and distributed by Michael Franjeh and further resources have been developed by Laura Thuleson from SIL. The Merei community was not included in the VESP programme and had no literacy materials developed prior to this survey. Table 1 lists the names of the schools included in the research and the number of teachers surveyed per school. Figure 1 gives an overview of the sample languages.

Table 1: list of schools surveyed and number of surveys

Rral (North Ambrym)		Vatlongos (Southeast Ambrym)		Merei (Big Bay, Santo)	
School	Surveys	School	Surveys	School	Surveys
Lonmelfarran	3	Senai	3	Malores	3
Ranon	2	Roromai	2	Vusvogo	4
Linbul	3	Pamal	1		
Fanla	2	Leleut	3		
Magam	2	Mbossung	2		
Tobol	3				

Teaching in Vernacular Language: Our sample

Figure 1: Languages in our sample

4.4 Limitations

The main limitations of the study were:

- There was insufficient time to visit every school in each community. In the Rral (North Ambrym) community we visited six out of nine schools. In the Merei community we visited two out of the three schools. Limited time in the rural communities was due to flight scheduling and other commitments during the research visit. We had also planned to include the Lewo community (Epi Island), however due to flight cancellations we were unable to visit.
- Sometimes the target teachers (principal, class one and class two teachers) were unavailable on the day of the survey. However, we interviewed those teachers who were available.
- We would have liked to have surveyed all teachers in early years education, from kindergarten to class six. However, this would have taken much more time than was available to the lead researcher.

5. Key findings and results

This section details our key findings. As we were unable to visit every school in each target community, except for the Vatlongos (Southeast Ambrym) community, the findings are intended to provide insights into rural communities' use of local vernacular language in schools. An overview of the key findings is given in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Key Findings Summary

Each of the following sections summarise quantitative and qualitative results for our three main research questions. Section 5.1 looks at teachers' confidence in using the community language and their training needs. Section 5.2 investigates the number of children who can speak the community language and their enjoyment of using the language in schools. Finally, section 5.3 looks at the available language resources in schools and what materials teachers said they need to teach effectively.

5.1 Teachers' use and confidence of community language and training needs

The 33 surveys covered teachers who taught from kindergarten level through to class six. Table 2 shows that some teachers taught just one level, others taught combined classes (e.g., class one and two) and others taught larger mixed groups (e.g., classes three to six) depending on the number of children in each year. Overall, the largest proportion of teachers surveyed taught in classes one and two.

Table 2: classes taught by the teachers surveyed

	Rral (North Ambrym)	Vatlongos (Southeast Ambrym)	Merei (Big Bay, Santo)	Total
Kindergarten	2	-	-	2
1-2	8	5	2	15
3-4	2	3	2	7
5-6	1	2	3	6
Mixed groups	2 (3-6; 2-3)	1 (1-6)	-	3

Overall, teachers' fluency in the main community language was high (79%). Figure 3 shows that teachers from the Vatlongos community reported the highest rates of fluency in the language (91%). Teachers from the Rral community reported the second highest rates of fluency (80%). Teachers from the Merei community reported the lowest rates of fluency (57%).

Figure 3: Teacher fluency

5.1.1 Teacher confidence in the community language

We asked teachers to rate their confidence in speaking, reading and writing in the main community language in the classroom (with 1 being the least confident and 5 being the most confident). Overall, teachers reported higher confidence in speaking the main community language than in reading and writing. Figure 4 shows that Teachers from the Rral language community had higher overall confidence in all areas of the main community

language than Merei and Vatlongos. Teachers from the Merei community had the lowest overall confidence across these three areas of language.

Figure 4: Teachers' confidence

Table 3 shows the results for teachers' confidence for speaking, reading and writing. Overall, there was slightly lower confidence for writing, but higher for reading and speaking when using the language in the classroom. Some teachers from the Vatlongos and Rral community had not tried to read or write in the language before, and these were excluded from the averages below.

Table 3: Teachers' average confidence in using the main community language in the classroom (1 being least confident and 5 being most confident)

	Speaking	Reading	Writing
Merei	3.1	4.4	3.7
Rral	4.5	4.8	4.1
Vatlongos	4.6	3.4	2.3

Vatlongos teachers also reported the lowest reading and writing skills, despite having already had literacy materials in their language provided by the Ministry of Education.

Teachers working in the Merei language community had the lowest confidence in speaking the language as a higher proportion of teachers surveyed were not fluent in the language. In other language communities there were also teachers from outside of the language community. However, after a number of years these teachers became fluent in the community language, resulting in higher confidence scores. Teachers from outside the community are not necessarily a barrier to teaching the community language.

What influenced confidence in the main community language?	Teacher Quotes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of vernacular language resources. • Some teachers commented that they had not even tried to read in the language. • Lots of teachers struggle with pronunciation of the language when reading. • Teachers struggled with the spelling system when reading and writing. • Training increases confidence. 	<p>"At first was hard, then after going through alphabet it is easy" Rral teacher</p> <p>"It will be easy if there were books" Merei teacher</p> <p>"I have to check the alphabet when I'm writing" Vatlongos teacher</p>

5.1.2 Further training requirements

We asked teachers to identify which aspects of the main community language they felt needed to be improved for them to effectively teach using it. Teachers identified writing and reading in the language as most needing improvement, reflecting their overall confidence in these areas. Speaking was not a major concern overall, except for those teachers who were not yet fluent in the main community language. However, in order to boost confidence and use the main community language effectively as the medium of instruction teachers require support in all aspects of the language.

Figure 5 shows the aspects of language that teachers in each community highlighted they wanted further support in. The Merei teachers had the highest need for improving their speaking and reading across all languages, though the lowest need for improvement in writing. Vatlongos had the highest need for training writing and a high need for reading. Both Rral and Vatlongos had low needs for training in speaking.

Figure 5: aspects of language for further training (four teachers identified writing stories, storytelling and sounds/phonics to be important)

<p>Further training identified by teachers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vernacular language workshops. • Phonics and spelling training. • Classroom resources. • Curriculum in the main community language. 	<p>“If there was a training session it would be helpful. Pronunciation of letters and reading practice” Rral teacher</p> <p>“It would be good to have training in all aspects of the language” Merei teacher</p> <p>“we need Phonics training. Writing and translating practice” Vatlongos teacher</p>
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5.1.3 Languages used in the classroom

We asked teachers to identify which languages they used the most and the least in their classroom. Overall the most used language was Bislama, with the main community language second, and English/French in third. The use of English/French the least may reflect two factors. First, the Vanuatu curriculum has a blended approach to teaching English/French, where they are introduced later in year 3, after using either Bislama or the main community language. Second, the teaching level with most teachers surveyed was class 1-2, where typically English/French are not yet used in the blended approach.

Figure 6 shows each community varied. The Merei community was not included in the MoET’s VESP program of introducing vernacular literacy. They used Bislama the most and Merei the least. The Rral community used the main community language the most, and English/French the least. The Vatlongos community used Bislama the most, and the main community language and English/French the least.

Figure 6: language use per language community

We also asked teachers what they use the main community language for in the classroom. The responses varied depending on how much the teachers used the main community languages in their classroom. Teachers who used the main community language the most in their classrooms would use it for everything. Other teachers would use the main community language in different ways, listed below. The main theme to emerge was the use of the main community language to translate explanations or instructions given in another language.

<p>Use of main community language in the classroom:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translations of explanations and instructions. • Playing and joking. • Naming objects. • Telling stories. • Practicing phonics and literacy. 	<p>“I only use Merei a little. Talk to individual children, not for whole group” Merei teacher</p> <p>“I use Rral to explain everything, write instructions, reading books” Rral teacher</p> <p>“I explain in Bislama, but if they don’t understand I explain in Vatlongos” Vatlongos teacher</p>
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5.1.4 Teachers’ enjoyment of the community language and impact on educational outcomes

We asked if the teachers enjoyed teaching using the main community language and if they thought it would benefit children’s educational outcomes. Teachers answered on a 5 point scale, from 1 being ‘don’t enjoy at all’, to 5 being ‘really enjoy’.

Overall there was a high average level of enjoyment of teaching using the community language. Figure 7 shows that teachers from the Vatlongos community had the highest average level of enjoyment, followed by Merei and then Rral.

Figure 7: Teachers' average enjoyment and educational outcomes

<p>Teachers enjoyed using language as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • it's the children's mother tongue . • it's their mother tongue. • it's easier for the children to understand. <p>Some teachers worried because:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They lack resources and training to teach properly. • Children can't write well in the language, so may impact their enjoyment. • Other languages may be better for teaching. 	<p>"If I knew the language then it would be good. I would be happy to learn" Rral teacher</p> <p>"I don't like teaching the language as there are no resources" Merei teacher</p> <p>"I think we waste time using Bislama. It would be better to do Vatlongos to English transition and not use Bislama as most children do not understand it." Vatlongos teacher</p>
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Teachers' enjoyment of teaching using the language would be improved if they had more resources and training. Teachers from outside the community showed a willingness to learn, but they will also need community support to learn the language.

Figure 7 also shows that there is a very high belief that children will benefit from being taught in the main community language. Teachers already use the main community languages to explain what is being taught, but they want more resources to teach effectively in the language. However, some teachers think that too much use of language will make the transition to English and French harder.

<p>Teachers believe that using the main community language will benefit children’s educational outcomes because:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It allows children to understand, explain and learn faster. • it’s their mother tongue. • it’s easier for the children to understand. <p>Some teachers worried because:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • they lack resources and training to teach properly. • it could influence children’s ability to learn other languages. • The children don’t have a high level in reading and writing in the main community languages. 	<p>“It’s their own language, so it’s easy for them” Rral teacher</p> <p>“100% it will help the children” Vatlongos teacher</p> <p>“it’s good for their understanding. But if they use Vatlongos, then they may use it too much and not use English. This happens in Bislama already” Vatlongos teacher</p> <p>“Children can learn Merei well, but there are no books in Merei. Everthing is in English” Merei teacher</p>
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5.2 Students’ knowledge and enjoyment of the community language

This section shows how many students in each community speak the main language, if they enjoy using the language in the classroom, and their abilities with different aspects of the language. Figure 8 shows the combined results, with the discussion of the data in the sections below.

Figure 8: Student metrics

5.2.1 How many students speak the community language

The number of students that were taught by the surveyed teachers varied across each language community (Merei = 131, Rral = 262, Vatlongos = 221). However, Figure 8 shows that there were similar ratios of students who could speak or couldn’t speak the main community language in the classes taught by the teachers surveyed. Overall, 91.7% of the children in the teachers’ classes could speak the main community language.

Due to time constraints we were unable to interview all teachers at every school in each of the three language communities. However, we believe that the figures for children not speaking the Rral language in the remaining schools in that community would be similar. However, the remaining school in the Merei

community would have a much more mixed ability with higher amounts of students from different language communities.

5.2.2 Students' enjoyment of the main community language

We asked the teachers if the students enjoy learning in the main community language or where the language is not used, if they think children will enjoy it. Teachers answered on a 5 point scale, from 1 being don't enjoy at all to 5 being really enjoy. On average, teachers reported high levels of enjoyment from students across all languages (see Figure 8 above).

<p>Teachers believe that children enjoy using the main community language because:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It helps them understand information better. • It helps them read and write better. • it's their mother tongue. <p>Some teachers report:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They want more training to give the students an enjoyable experience. • There can be mixed levels of enjoyment as not all students speak the language. • Some students prefer other languages. 	<p>"They will own their education" Vatlongos teacher</p> <p>"They will like it, to take Merei and translate into French. They will understand quickly. It's a long process from Merei-Bislama-French. They should learn Bislama when older" Merei teacher</p> <p>"It's their language. Communication is easier in Rral" Rral teacher</p> <p>"Children want to learn English. They know language already, so they want to know English" Rral teacher</p>
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5.2.3 Children's abilities with aspects of the community language

Teachers reported that children found speaking in the main community language easy. However, most teachers highlighted that children found reading and writing to be difficult. Figure 8 shows that the Rral language community had the lowest scores in reading and writing, showing that they need less support in this area. The Rral community also use their language the most in the classroom (Figure 6).

<p>Teachers report :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many haven't started to teach reading and writing in the main community language due to lack of resources and training. • Children struggle with the spelling and phonics of the community language. • Children with access to language resources and trained teachers find most aspects of the language easier. 	<p>"There are no resources; it's hard to read and write" Merei teacher</p> <p>"I'm not teaching in language yet. I've not introduced reading and writing yet" Merei teacher</p> <p>"Children are just starting to learn (reading and writing), but they are good for their level" Rral teacher</p> <p>"The curriculum is in Bislama and French: no chance to use language for reading and writing" Rral teacher</p> <p>"It will be hard (reading and writing), but with proper training we can do it" Vatlongos teacher</p> <p>"If I teach in vernacular it will be easy to write and read. In Kindy they use vernacular." Vatlongos teacher</p>
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5.3 Community Language Resources

5.3.1 Current community language resources in schools

The majority of the Merei teachers had no resources for teaching the language in schools. Only one teacher reported having access to an alphabet poster. Figure 9 shows the type of resources per school. The schools in the Rral community had the largest amount of types of resources. However these were not available in every school. VESP MoET literacy materials had been produced for the Rral and Vatlongos communities, however not every school in these communities had copies remaining.

Figure 9: Language resource type per language community

<p>Teacher’s say :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current resources are not good as they are only in English or Bislama. • More reading materials are needed • Current resources should be translated into local languages and dialects. • Phonics resources are needed to support children. • More copies of the current resources are needed. 	<p>“We need materials in the Endu dialect as children don’t know all the words in the other dialect” Vatlongos teacher</p> <p>“A hurricane destroyed lots of literacy materials” Rral teacher</p> <p>“There aren’t many copies [of the VESP materials] – we could do with some more!” Vatlongos teacher</p>
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5.3.2 Self-made resources

Just over half the teachers surveyed make their own vernacular literacy resources. Figure 10 shows that the Merei community made the least amount of resources, whereas the Rral community made the most. We note that the Rral community has received prior training and support in this area from linguists and Bible translators.

Figure 10: Self-made resources

The following are a list of some of the key resources teachers have made and Figure 11 shows examples:

- Use natural resources for naming/counting
- Draw pictures with vernacular names
- Matching game – words to pictures
- Draw letters which are cut out so children can spell words
- Create big/class story books
- Flashcards

Figure 11: Examples of self-made resources

5.3.3 Resources teachers need

The majority of teachers require more literacy materials to effectively teach in the main community language. The following is a list of the main requirements from teachers:

- Alphabet resources: phonics, posters, flashcards
- Books: big/class story books,
- Dictionaries
- Teachers' resources: Teachers' guides, syllabus, curriculum and lesson plans
- Resources on traditional and ecological knowledge: local names of animals and plants
- Traditional stories
- Maths and numeracy materials
- Different text types: recount, procedure, descriptive, narrative, information and explanation
- Multi-media resources in the language: videos, audio
- Health
- Science
- Resources on grammar (e.g., verbs, adjectives etc.)

6. Conclusions

This report set out to understand:

1. Teachers' confidence in using the main community language as the medium of instruction and their further training needs.
2. Children's enjoyment of using the main community language in class and what aspects they find hard.
3. What resources are available and what needs to be developed.

Teachers

We found that teachers were most confident in speaking the community language, but their confidence in reading and writing the language was much lower.

Teachers reported high levels of enjoyment when using the main community language. They felt that children benefit from a greater understanding of the subjects being taught when using the main community language.

Overall the language used most in the classrooms was Bislama, though each community varied in its use of the main community language, showing that implementation of vernacular literacy is currently patchy.

All teachers would benefit from further training in phonics and the community language alphabets, to increase their confidence and to enable them to teach using the language more effectively.

Children

Across the schools surveyed in the three communities more than 90% of children speak the main community language. However, not all schools and all teachers were interviewed in these three communities. Though based on discussions with community members, similar rates of fluency would be found throughout the rest of the Rral and Vatlongos communities. For the Merei community, there may be more mixed levels of fluency.

The teachers reported that students showed high levels of enjoyment when using the main community language. Even for teachers who were not using the main community language reported that the children would be eager to learn in their own language.

Teachers reported that students found reading and writing in the main community language hard, which are the same aspects the teachers also found hard themselves.

Resources

Current vernacular literacy materials varied widely across communities and across schools within each community. For the Vatlongos and Rral communities, some schools reported that the MoET VESP materials developed had not arrived, or that they had been lost due to natural disasters. Teachers saw the need for further resource development. Some teachers had created their own resources for teaching using the main community language; however this too varied widely.

Summary

Teachers and students show great levels of support for using the main community language as the medium of instruction. Their enjoyment of using the community languages shows support for current education policies around using these languages in Kindergarten and years one and two before transitioning to either English or French.

However teachers require much more support from the Ministry of Education and Training in order to teach effectively. We highlight several recommendations for moving forward.

7. Recommendations

Our recommendations are specific to the three language communities involved in the study. However, these recommendations may be useful for other language communities in rural areas outside of the main urban centres of Port Vila and Luganville.

1. Teacher Training:

- a. Further support for teachers in phonics of the main community languages.
- b. Teachers from outside the community require support in acquiring the community language.

2. Resources:

- a. A fuller understanding of what vernacular resources are currently available in each school and reprinting of VESP materials where necessary.
- b. Teachers require further support in developing their own literacy resources.

To improve teachers' confidence, training workshops need to be tailored for each community. One way to achieve this would be to strengthen local and international networks. For example, by working closely with external linguists who work with different language communities through the Vanuatu Cultural Centre, and with the Summer Institute of Linguistics (SIL) in Port Vila.

Teachers often move to new schools, so training should not be one-off, but at regular intervals for continued support. Teachers from outside the language community would greatly benefit from continued community support in learning the community language. Furthermore, teachers from within a language community require continued support to improve reading and writing skills. A teacher-led initiative in one school in the Rral community (North Ambrym) was implemented, where both teachers external to the community and local teachers meet on a weekly basis to improve their speaking, reading and writing skills. MoET should investigate these local initiatives and support further roll-out of similar grass-roots strategies across other communities. Furthermore, teachers who are from a different language community to the one they are teaching in should only teach classes one and two once they become fluent in the local language.

Teachers cannot teach without resources. What is available varies across each school and community. The Curriculum Development Unit should obtain reports from principals of each school to get a fuller picture of what is currently available and reprint resources where necessary. Implementing the full list of resources that teachers have identified would be costly, but providing training for teachers to create their own materials would provide a cost-effective solution. Teachers should be trained through workshops in resource development to create big/class books, traditional stories, posters, flashcards, alphabet and numeracy resources, and lesson plans. We note that this type of training has been delivered in the Rral community before, which has led to the highest amount of self-made resources compared to the other communities surveyed here. Other materials such as dictionaries, language curriculum, and for different subjects such as health and science could be developed at a later stage once teachers' confidence in reading and writing have improved.